

D1.3: Open call documentation 3

*Documentation for the IMPETUS
Open Call for Funding 2025*

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Deliverable description

Text

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***PU:** Public / **CO:** Confidential Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services) / **CI:** Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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1. Summary

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of the documentation for the third open call for funding in the IMPETUS project, which includes the following documents:

- Challenge Definitions
- Guide for Applicants
- Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)
- Application form
- Declaration of Honour
- EasyChair user guide
- Draft Contract(s)
- Call Announcement

These documents will be used for the open call, which will run from the 7th of January to the 13th of March 2025. Especially the FAQ will be continuously updated as we receive questions during the call period; all other documents have been revised based on feedback and observations from the second open call carried out in 2024.

Please note that, while the timeline for the open call for funding is aligned with the call for nominations for the European Union Prize for Citizen Science, this document refers to the call for funding only.

2. Purpose and role in IMPETUS

This document was created primarily by KCL who will implement the open call for funding. The call documentation is largely an updated version of the same documents used successfully in the first and second open calls, considering some learnings from the first implementation of the process, as outlined in D1.5, Open Call Summary 2.

2.1 Contribution towards project objectives

This deliverable is key to achieving milestone 7 of the project: Open Call 3, and contributes to the following objectives/key results: “Call challenges defined (including with citizen panel), relevant criteria and processes (i.e. evaluation) defined, and call and related documentation published.”

It includes all the documentation relevant to run the call, which is already in place on the IMPETUS website at the time of writing. In this third open call, we aim to reach 450 applications, and recruit 34 kickstarting and 11 sustaining citizen science initiatives. Results of the call will be summarised at the end of the selection period in D1.6 Open call summary report 3.

2.2 Relationship with other WPs

As with the second open call, the Guide for applicants especially was developed in close alignment with all other WPs, and with extensive feedback from all consortium members and reviewers engaged in the process in the first round.

It includes a timeline of the negotiation and acceleration, as well as commitments of the participants during these periods, such as training and reporting requirements, which were discussed and aligned with WPs 2 (Accelerator), 4 (Policy), 5 (Impact) and 7 (Project Management).

We also decided to continue to align the timelines between the open calls for the accelerator, and nominations for the Prize, in order to maximise the effectiveness of outreach activities, and increase the number of applications for both areas. This has been highlighted in the documentation, and the funding call will remain open a few days longer than the Prize call, to prevent applicants applying for one call only due to the conflicting deadlines.

3. Challenge definition

The **first challenge** for the IMPETUS open call was defined by the consortium, based on the indicators for sustainable development goals and goals of the European Green Deal. The theme ***Citizen Science for Circular Economies*** was set out in the Grant Agreement. Both goals frameworks and

indicators were revised to select the most appropriate elements which could be addressed through citizen science. In addition to the two focus SDGs (7 – Affordable and Clean Energy; 12 – Responsible Consumption and Production), the IMPETUS consortium decided to include both SDG11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities; and SDG 13 – Climate Action in this challenge, which were initially planned as more transversal themes. As outlined in D 1.2, this call was adjusted to focus more solidly on sustainability and climate.

The **second challenge** was defined by the IMPETUS Citizen Panel. The panel was recruited from citizen science practitioners in October 2022 and defined the highly successful *Cities for Life* and *Justice and Equity* challenges for the first and second open calls respectively. The panel was expanded in September 2023 to include 20 members, which added ten and replaced three members who had dropped out. A final expansion to recruit 10 new members was carried out in September 2024 leading to a total of 30 panel members.

The purpose of the citizen panel is threefold:

1. define challenges for the open accelerator call – the method we use to recruit citizen science initiatives that will receive funding and support;
2. contribute to the nomination and selection of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science; and
3. help spread the word about citizen science in Europe, and Impetus' mission.

The panel members are citizen science practitioners from across Europe, and consists of twenty members, who were selected based on a variety of criteria, including gender, expertise and geographical diversity. Individual member profiles are available on the IMPETUS website:

<https://impetus4cs.eu/about/citizen-panel/>.

The new panel first got together on the 11th October 2024, where they brainstormed to define a list of topics that they felt would be relevant for citizen science to address. This was then expanded through collaborative online tools (predominantly Google Docs). The initial list included:

1. Climate Education
2. Carbon Capture
3. Art for Change
4. AI and Digital Inclusion
5. Perceptions
6. Fair Society

7. Education
8. Energy
9. Age
10. Small Communities
11. Democracy
12. War/Peace
13. Economy
14. Identity/Belonging
15. Mobilisation
16. Methods and Novel Citizen Science

Two subsequent calls took place on the 31st of October and the 15th of November. These calls were used to create further suggestions, develop existing suggestions further, gather feedback and comments and begin to create a consensus on the most popular suggestions. Following this, a survey was circulated to participants asking them to rank the options with *Citizen Science for a Fair and Just Society* ultimately receiving the highest score. In the last week of November, challenge text was drafted and this was collaboratively edited with the panel. The panel text is provided in Annex 1.

4. Changes from last open call

The key changes that were made to the documentation overall include:

- In the **Challenges**
 - o Updated topics in line with new SDGs to focus and citizen panel preferences.
- In the **Guide for Applicants**
 - o Updated dates and timeline to match the third open call timeline.
 - o Added explanation of the need to read and understand the draft contract prior to making a submission.
- In the **FAQ**
 - o Added details of the rolling eligibility check offered to applicants for the third open call.
 - o Added explanatory question and answer regarding the need to read and understand the draft contract prior to making an application.
- On **EasyChair submission platform**
 - o Added a question asking participants to confirm that they have read and in principle agree with the draft contract
 - o Removed upload option for letters of support initially introduced to facilitate applications to the *Citizen Science with and for Communities* challenge in 2024.
- In **EasyChair User Guide**
 - o Updated images to better reflect challenge names and new topic areas
 - o Added an image and clarifying text regarding the question concerning the draft contract
- In the **Draft Contracts**
 - o Added a draft contract for Individual Beneficiaries and Multiple Beneficiaries. This is new for 2025 and was added in response to difficulties arising at negotiation from applicants expecting changes to the contracts or being unable to sign the contract as intended.

5. Open Call documentation

The relevant documents are available from our website, where they will also be made available to applicants during the call:

1. Challenge Definitions (see Annex 1)
2. Call Announcement (see Annex 2)
3. [Draft Subgrantee Agreements](#)
4. [Guide for Applicants](#)
5. [Frequently Asked Questions \(FAQ\)](#)
6. [EasyChair user guide](#)
7. [Application form](#)
8. [Declaration of Honour](#)

6. Annex1 – Challenges

Challenge 1: Citizen Science for Circular Communities

Why this matters

Citizen Science engages volunteers in a range of scientific activities. This helps educate and inform citizens in the subject matter and leads to a greater public understanding of how science and scientists work. Participation in Citizen Science can increase trust in science and expert opinions, enhance critical thinking, and ultimately fight misinformation, disinformation and fake news. Scientists can learn from Citizen Science about what people genuinely care about, the impact their work has or should have in society, and become more participatory, by involving volunteers early on in co-designing the research, collecting, cleaning, and analysing the data, documenting the results, and sharing the recognition.

Citizen Science is playing an ever more important role in how researchers and innovators engage with society, and how they contribute to common concerns. However, Citizen Science sometimes struggles to achieve recognition and impact because citizen and ‘professional’ science practices differ, and citizen scientists have a harder time gaining access to local stakeholders and policy makers. Results of Citizen Science are chronically underutilised, although we know that they can add value to virtually everything from meeting Green Deal and UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets to boosting social and environmental innovations, all while being closely aligned with local communities.

While Green Deal and SDG targets may seem abstract for many citizen scientists, their projects may already be working toward monitoring them, through activities such as environmental measurements (for example air, water or soil quality), or monitoring (for example insect or bird observations).

What we are looking for

In our Open Call 2025, IMPETUS is looking for Citizen Science projects that contribute to sustainable development goals related to the theme of “Citizen Science for Circular Communities”. Specifically, we are interested in projects that address one or more of the following topics, which are related to SDGs #7, #11, #12, and #3:

- **Resource management:** Encouraging responsible and (re-)use of resources (e.g. natural resources, energy); preventing waste and pollution of all kinds; education and awareness raising about sustainable lifestyles with special attention to circularity.

- **Infrastructure & housing:** Availability, efficiency, sustainability and resilience of suitable accommodation and infrastructure, including energy, HVAC, and public transport.
- **Disaster resilience:** Safeguarding people, their homes, jobs, and culture, in the face of natural disasters, including those caused by climate change; community participation in disaster preparedness, prevention, and recovery, and adaptation and mitigation practices.

Applicants should contribute to at least one of these topics, and enable the monitoring of at least one [established indicator](#), by providing monitoring data, or directly contributing to their achievement at local, regional, or national level.

How we select projects

We particularly welcome applications from projects that are run by, or actively involve, underrepresented groups and their public representation. This includes those belonging to groups at risk of social exclusion and discrimination, such as refugees, ethnic minorities, the LGBTQ+ community, those with disabilities; or from [lower-middle income countries](#); as well as projects that focus on inclusion dimensions of their research.

All projects **will also be assessed against criteria of equality, diversity, equity, openness, and potential impact on policy.**

IMPETUS has an [inclusive view of Citizen Science](#) initiatives, which can have a wide-ranging scope of scientific and social activities that engage citizens and aim to deliver scientific advancement and social benefits, support communities, and foster an open and inclusive civil society.

Eligible projects could include but are not limited to:

- Citizen engaged in digital humanities research
- Initiatives that incorporate characteristics of Citizen Science as defined by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)
- Science and research communication with citizens
- Participatory artistic-led research
- Science education that engages citizens

What we offer

Successful applicants will receive funding and support to deliver a seven-month project. Support will include training and expert guidance from a range of experts within and beyond the IMPETUS consortium, as well as peer-to-peer support and exchange. Projects can apply for two kinds of grants, depending on their current development stage:

- Projects that are no more than six months into their Citizen Science journey and are yet to establish a community and/or data collection and processing procedures, can apply for a **Kickstarting grant**, worth 20,000 €.
- Projects that are more advanced, with established processes, an engaged community, and initial evidence of impact, can apply for a **Sustaining grant**, worth 10,000 €. We expect these grants to be awarded for the continuation, enhancing of impact, and/or further establishment of existing projects.

The funds provided can be spent on personnel costs, equipment, consumables, travel, subcontracting to other entities, and indirect expenditure (calculated as 25% of the total direct costs), in accordance with Horizon Europe guidelines.

Challenge 2: Citizen Science for a Fair and Just Society

Why this matters

Social Fairness is a priority for the European Commission, while ‘leaving no-one behind’ is the central pledge of the UN 2030 Agenda. Recent events such as the Covid 19 Pandemic, cost of living crisis and global unrest have posed unique challenges to fairness in European societies. Societies are evolving, with changes such as the rise of generative AI technologies, increased adoption (and weaponisation) of social media and the acceleration of climate change impacting diverse communities in different ways. At the same time, the democratic principles underpinning European society are under threat. Social views are growing increasingly polarised while societal divisions are increasing. Citizen science can support communities and individuals in diverse ways through educating them on these evolving issues and topics; creating opportunities for them to take a leading role in community action or empowering them to protect democracy and ensure all voices are heard.

For this challenge, we particularly recognise that novel approaches to citizen science, using art, storytelling, multimedia or other technologies, may also foster participation of marginalized and underserved groups. We therefore particularly encourage submissions proposing novel or deeper forms of volunteer engagement, as well as projects from the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences. However, this does not prevent submissions using other disciplinary or methodological approaches.

We focus on three distinct but related topics pertaining to promoting a fair and just society:

- **Democracy and Peace:** Democratic institutions across Europe are under attack. Trust in those institutions is low and some groups, particularly young people, are disillusioned by democracy. Social divisions are high and peace is under threat. We see citizen science as an opportunity to promote social cohesion and understanding between different groups, fostering democracy and peace.
- **Inclusion:** While novel societal and technological developments pose opportunities for citizens, not every community has benefited equally from these opportunities. Some groups, such as rural communities, the elderly or those of lower socioeconomic status (to name but a few) have found it harder to exploit these opportunities and risk being left behind. Citizen science has the potential to empower these communities, giving them the opportunity to advocate for their views and for change.

- **Public Trust, Education and Empowerment:** Trust in science and public institutions is at risk and misinformation is increasingly common. Citizen science has the potential to educate communities, giving them an opportunity to experience, learn from and contribute to the scientific process. Collaborations between researchers, academics and stakeholders such as artists can be instrumental in creating engaging, accessible content which resonates with and informs diverse audiences. Through these strategies, citizen science initiatives can bridge the gap between research and communities, fostering trust, understanding and action.

What we are looking for

In our Open Call 2025, IMPETUS is looking for Citizen Science projects that contribute to the theme of “Citizen Science for a Fair and Just Society”. Specifically, we are interested in projects that address one or more of the following topics, which may relate but are not limited to SDGs #4, #5, #10, and #16:

- **Democracy and Peace** and promoting, safeguarding or enhancing understanding of democracy, the democratic process and systems or social cohesion.
- **Inclusion** through promoting inclusion; understanding factors which lead to exclusion and inclusion; empowering marginalised communities or promoting inclusion in novel societal or technological developments.
- Promoting **Public Trust, Education and Empowerment** where a broad approach to education is taken and may involve traditional educational settings or education through engagement in citizen science.

Applicants should aim to implement projects that contribute to research that enables solutions to these issues. Projects that address topics in or through social and artistic research are explicitly included in this call.

How we select projects

We particularly welcome applications from projects that are run by, or actively involve, underrepresented groups and their public representation. This includes those belonging to groups at risk of social exclusion and discrimination, such as refugees, ethnic minorities, the LGBTQ+ community, those with disabilities; or from [lower-middle income countries](#); as well as projects that focus on inclusion dimensions of their research.

All projects **will also be assessed against criteria of equality, diversity, equity, openness, and potential impact on policy.**

IMPETUS has an [inclusive view of Citizen Science](#) initiatives, which can have a wide-ranging scope of scientific and social activities that engage citizens and aim to deliver scientific advancement and social benefits, support communities, and foster an open and inclusive civil society.

Eligible projects could include but are not limited to:

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The funds provided can be spent on personnel costs, equipment, consumables, travel, subcontracting to other entities, and indirect expenditure (calculated as 25% of the total direct costs), in accordance with Horizon Europe guidelines.

7. Annex 2 – Call Announcement

TEMPLATE for FP7 Competitive Calls and

1. H2020 Financial Support to Third Parties

1. To publish a call on the Funding & Tenders Portal (F&TP), the Project Officer must send to the F&TP team at least the following information:

	Information to be provided by the project consortium
Call title:	IMPETUS Citizen Science Challenge 2025
Full name of the EU funded project:	IMPETUS
Project acronym:	IMPETUS
Grant agreement number:	101058677
Call opening date:	07/01/2025 at 12:00 (Brussels time)
Call deadline:	13/03/2024 at 12:00 (Brussels time)
Expected duration of participation:	Participation for successful applicants will last 7 months
Total EU funding available:	790,000 EUR Funding for kickstarting projects: 20,000 EUR (34x) Funding for sustaining projects: 10,000 EUR (11x)
Submission & evaluation process:	<p>Submission process:</p> <p>Applications will be made in English, online via the following platform: https://easychair.org/my/conference?conf=impetus4cs</p> <p>Applications will consist of a short proposal presenting the idea, implementation, resources and impact, as well as administrative information and a declaration of honour. The short proposal should follow the template available in the IMPETUS ‘guide for applicants’ and must not exceed 4 pages.</p> <p>Evaluation process:</p> <p>The evaluation will be divided into the following stages:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Eligibility check: the funding is available to legal entities established in a country or territory eligible to receive Horizon Europe grants. Every entity is allowed to participate in one application, either on its own or as part of a consortium. 2. Proposal review: each proposal will be assessed against four criteria: idea, implementation, team and community, and impact. 3. Applicants will be informed of the results and short-listed candidates will be invited to an online interview with an expert panel. <p>See IMPETUS’ ‘guide for applicants’ accessible from the submission platform for more details on the evaluation process: www.impetus4cs.eu/opencall</p>

Further information:	opencall@IMPETUS4cs.eu
Task description:	<p>The IMPETUS Open Call is intended to support the implementation and sustainability of citizen science projects addressing the IMPETUS challenge. For this call we are inviting projects that focus on the themes of <i>Citizen Science for Circular Communities</i> and <i>Citizen Science for a Fair and Just Society</i>.</p> <p>Successful applicants will be expected to design, implement and present the findings from a related citizen science projects over the course of seven months, and actively engage in the IMPETUS Accelerator, including mentoring, networking, and training sessions.</p> <p>Applications which engage citizens in scientific activities producing new results, which are of mutual benefit to citizen scientists and project administrators alike will be prioritised. We particularly encourage projects that address marginalised, disadvantaged or vulnerable groups to engage in citizen science and expect that where possible, projects funded through the IMPETUS open call should be openly accessible to all.</p>